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As we hurtle towards the end of the year here's a little light reading for you. We have a great interview with University of Portsmouth LNL Stefana Juncu, lots of events and resources and put your thinking hats on because nominations for the 2025 Dorothy Bishop Prize are now open. And here's a food related thought to see you through the festive season from LNL Stefana: '**open research is not the cherry on top of the cake, it is the cake!**' Enjoy.

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Spotlight on Portsmouth

Our recent [blog](#) spotlights the work of [Stefana Juncu](#) at the University of Portsmouth. Stef is a member of UoPen and is involved in many open research activities and initiatives. Read more [here](#).

Dorothy Bishop Prize - nominations please

Have you, or someone you know, achieved or contributed something special to improve research or promote open research practices? UKRN are seeking nominations for the Dorothy Bishop Prize, which recognises and rewards the achievements of early career researchers based in the UK. There will be up to three awards. The winners will each be awarded a prize of £500 (in the form of Amazon vouchers) and a “Doscar” (a Lego minifigure of Dorothy Bishop). You can nominate yourself, or nominate another person **with their permission**.

Nominations open 11 December 2024 and close at midnight GMT on Sunday 26 January 2025.

The UKRN Dorothy Bishop Prize Task Force will shortlist based on:

- Evidence of a contribution to the promotion and delivery of activities that have served to improve research or promote open scholarship. Contributions will be evaluated relative to opportunity and access to opportunity.
- Alignment with the [mission and values](#) of UKRN.

A task force consisting of members of the UKRN Advisory Committees will evaluate the nominations and create a shortlist. The winner(s) will then be chosen by the Supervisory Board. Nominees will be notified about whether they have been shortlisted in February 2025. The winner or winners will be announced at the UKRN Annual Meeting in March 2025.

Nomination form: <https://tinyurl.com/UKRN-Dorothy-Bishop-Prize-2025>

(clicking on the yes/no radio buttons opens up further pages on the form)

Octopus.ac integration with government database

The UKRN initiative [Octopus.ac](#) has integrated with the UK Government [Areas of Research Interest database](#), a UKRI-funded platform. One of the key benefits is that researchers can cite their ARI-linked work on Octopus to get credit for the societal impact of their research. This could help secure potential funding, while providing government departments with fresh ideas and insights as well as a broader range of academic contacts. Read more [here](#). There is also a [free online webinar](#) on 20th February 2025 where you can learn more.

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Welcomes and goodbyes

Please welcome new LNLs joining UKRN, and thank you to those stepping out of the role to move onto other exciting opportunities! We try to report all changes but if we miss you, please let us know and we will include you in the next newsletter.

Please welcome:

Four new LNLs within the University of Edinburgh

[Gillian Currie](#) - a Postdoctoral Researcher who specialises in systematic review and meta-analysis of preclinical studies.

[Huayi Huang](#) - a Research Fellow in population health sciences with a focus on qualitative research.

[Jamie McQueen](#) - Research Data Manager for the Institute of Regeneration and Repair.

[Sarah Stanton](#) - Senior Lecturer in the Department of Psychology.

Huge thanks, goodbye and good luck:

Will Cawthorn who has recently moved to the IL role within Edinburgh.

We are currently looking for new LNLs within University of Exeter, University of Gloucestershire, University of Greenwich, and University of Sunderland. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

LNL Webinar

[Transparency and Openness Promotion \(TOP\) Guidelines](#)

11th February 2025 1:00 pm – 2:00 pm

[The Transparency and Openness Promotion \(TOP\) Guidelines](#) are a policy framework designed to enhance the verifiability of empirical research claims in research. The Center for Open Science (COS) has recently announced a major update to the TOP Guidelines, effective from January 2025. A preprint introducing the updated TOP framework is available [here](#). The revisions are the result of an extensive consultation process with the TOP Advisory Board, currently chaired by Sean Grant and co-chaired by the [University of Chester LNL Suzanne Stewart](#). Suzanne will be moving up to the chair role for 2025 and this workshop is a great opportunity to learn from your fellow LNL about how this update applies to your own research and how you might use it in your LNL activities.

Register [here](#)

UKRN Webinar

[Update on UKRN projects STAR and METEOR/COMET](#)

30th January 1:00 - 3:00

An update on the [STAR \(Sustainable & TrAnSPARENT Research data\)](#), [METEOR \(METa-research for the Enhancement Of Research culture\)](#) and [COMET](#) research projects. The STAR project assessed the development and implementation of open data policy and practice higher education institutions. METEOR investigated the use of metaresearch evidence in institutional decision-making that affects research culture. Both projects conducted qualitative interviews and focus groups with professional staff at 20 UK universities. While the STAR project is ending, we will also hear about how during 2025 the COMET project will be building on and scaling up the work started by METEOR.

Speakers: Jess Wheeler, Pen-Yuan Hsing and Amy Devenney, University of Bristol

Register [here](#)

Key UKRN resource updated

[Open Research: Examples of good practice, and resources across disciplines](#)

The 2025 edition of Open Research: Examples of good practice, and resources across disciplines is now available. This newly updated preprint is the gift that keeps on giving. It's a great way to demonstrate why and how open research is relevant to a particular discipline. LNL Stef Juncu notes that graduate students found it very useful. Details are also available on the UKRN website: [Open Research Across Disciplines](#).

LNL Regional Groups

Some LNLs have been meeting up through the regional groups. Please let us know if you do get together. There is some budget available through early 2025 to cover transport and light catering costs. Let us know what you talked about and how these meetings can be useful to the LNL community. Thanks.

Reading recommendations

[Our future, we decide: five ways to reform the scientific publication process](#)

Based on discussions at the 2023 Danish Diabetes and Endocrine Academy Postdoc Summit, Dall and colleagues have identified five areas where improvements could be made: AI, the peer review bottleneck; replicability, accessibility and impact metrics. Read more [here](#).

That's *not* all folks

We are delighted to announce that the Community Project has been granted a no-cost extension to the end of May 2025. The newsletters will continue. If you would like to contribute just get in touch, we would love to hear from you. It's your newsletter! contact@ukrn.org